

Innovation Presentation Outline

The marriage between Living Labs and citizen science: Applied insights and future directions

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Abstract

Citizen-centric knowledge generation (citizen science) and citizen-centric open innovation (living labs) are powerful, complementary approaches for citizen engagement in the process of societal transformation. However, even joining fundamental traits, both Citizen Science and Living Labs communities have historically suffered absence of systematic connection, and institutional initiatives and policies around open science and open innovation have kept silos, with the negative consequence of the absence of a firm link between high quality scientific knowledge and impactful innovation. In this work, we support the most needed acceleration of the approach between the communities of Citizen Science and Living Labs. For the identification of common traits and opportunities for collaboration, we designed and implemented a series of specific workshops, based on a collection of four case studies, which were curated from contributions from different institutional partners in varied contexts, reflecting practical dimensions of participatory science and citizen-centric innovation. Two specific workshops were carried out at the major conferences on Citizen Science (ECSA'24) and Living Labs (ENoLL'24), developing as an outcome a joint narrative for the joint added value offered. Our work shows relevant evidence on common values and methods, clear examples of collaboration, and a proposal for an institutional roadmap and further steps.

Key words

Citizen Science, Living Labs, Open Science, Open Innovation, Policy information

Outline

Citizen engagement appears as a fundamental tool for addressing current challenges, from two complementary perspectives: the generation of new scientific evidence (Citizen Science) and the generation of impactful and transformative innovation processes (Living Labs). However, both Citizen Science and Living Labs communities have suffered from absence of systematic connection between them, and institutional initiatives and policies on open science and open innovation did not profit from their approach. The absence of a firm link between high quality scientific knowledge and impactful innovation is hindering positive societal transformation, and it contributes to atomized efforts and reduced ambition for systemic change. Particularly, there are strong examples of the contribution of Living Labs and Citizen Science to evidence-based processes supported by iterative, and collaborative approaches -taking in consideration dimensions such as depth on engagement, geographical scope, or development of awareness-, which also constitute valuable references to policymaking and inclusive governance of their respective ecosystems.

In our work, we curated 4 specific real case-studies in which evidence of living lab and citizen science-related activities were present, in the contexts of Green and Climate, Energy, Health and Cultural Heritage and AI. The dimensions developed in the cases comprise: 1) Main interests, challenges addressed and societal relevance, 2) Governance level (local/regional/national), 3) Who generally generates the challenges addressed in the LL, 4) Funding model (private, sponsors etc.), 5) Services offered, 6) Stakeholders involved and level of involvement. Two workshops at ECSA'24 and ENoLL'24 developed a joint narrative using a four-phase co-creation method on real case studies.

This work has been developed in the context of the MoU between ENoLL and ECSA [2]. The full study will be published and accessible in open science format during the OLLD'25.

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